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Research Article

IMPORTANCE OF AGNOR STAINING IN AMEOBLASTOMA HISTOLOGICAL GRADING

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Abstract:

Objective: To compare different histological variants of ameloblastoma in terms of proliferative activity, to use histochemical methods of AgNORs and to classify different types of ameloblastomas.

Place and Duration: In the Department of Pathology of Services Hospital Lahore for two year duration from January 2017 to December 2018.

Methods: A cross-sectional study of 50 surgical specimens collected using a non-probability sampling technique of ameloblastoma was selected. All ameloblastoma variants (histological variants) were collected from all ages and sexes. The decay and unfixed tissues were removed from the study and all cases were determined by the presence of bone. All selected samples were fixed in 10% neutral formalin and treated with hematoxylin and eosin at the Pathology Department for initial selection. These sections were initially reviewed by two pathologists by examining several hematoxylin and eosin-stained tumor slides (mean, 2.5 slides per tumor, range, 2-8), and were diagnosed with consensus.

Results: The mean age of the patients was 39.9 ± 15.1 between 12 and 80 years. There were 37 (76%) males and 13 (25%) females in this study. When AgNOR's mean values were examined in 4 study groups, the mean value of AgNOR was higher for acanthomatous, ie 3.15 ± 0.30 and the follicular variant was lower for 1.39 ± 0.82 . Comparison of MAgNOR was performed using ANOVA and mean mAgNOR was different in 4 groups and p value was calculated as <0.001 . In the histological variants, the association of mAgNOR 3.0 value was observed when the association of threshold value was observed ($p = 0.003$). Patients with MAgNOR > 3.0 were only in the desmoplastic and acanthomatous groups. Similarly, the relationship of pAgNOR > 5.0 was significant with histological variants ($P < 0.001$). All desmoplastic and acanthomatous cases had pAgNOR > 5.0 . The size relationship was significant with histological variables ($p = 0.001$). When the desmoplastic variants were in the dimensions of +1 and +2, acanthomatous was only +2. There were very few follicular cases in the +1 dimension. Similar results were found for the dispersion to be $p < 0.001$ with histological variables.

Conclusion: AgNOR staining technique may be useful in histopathological classification of ameloblastoma. The quantitative and qualitative evaluation of silver nitrate staining reflects a more malignant potential in acanthomatous and desmoplastic variants than in follicular and plexiform varieties.

Key words: AgNOR, ameloblastoma, histological classification.

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INTRODUCTION:

Ameloblastoma is the most common oral tumor originating from odontogenic epithelium. The relative frequency is equal to the combined frequency of all odontogenic tumors except odontomas [1]. They are generally benign, but are characterized by local recurrences after biological treatment. The clinical and histological features of ameloblastoma are interesting, contradictory, paradoxical and incompatible with clinical destructive behavior and benign histological appearance [2]. Nuclear organization regions (NOR) are DNA rings which are copied to ribosomal RNA. They can be visualized as intranuclear black spots by histochemical staining with colloid silver solution [3]. Silver stained nucleolar proteins (AgNOR) were counted in various bone tumors of the jaw. Histological variants of ameloblastoma have different results [4]. Follicular ameloblastoma is thought to be more common than plexiform ameloblastoma as it shows a smaller AgNOR area and a higher AgNOR number [5]. The combination of counting and measuring the area of the AgNOR points showed a significant overall difference between the AgNOR profiles of the follicular and plexiform variants of the ameloblastoma; decides the effect of chemotherapy and prognosis [6].

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This cross-sectional study was chosen in 50 surgical specimens collected using the appropriate non-probability sampling technique of ameloblastoma was held in the Department of Pathology of Services Hospital Lahore for two year duration from January 2017 to December 2018.

Histological ameloblastoma variants were taken at all ages and both sexes. The decay and unfixed tissues were removed from the study and all cases were determined by the presence of bone. All selected samples were fixed in 10% neutral formalin and treated with hematoxylin and eosin at the Pathology department for initial selection. These sections were initially reviewed by two pathologists by examining several hematoxylin and eosin-stained tumor slides (mean, 2.5 slides per tumor, range, 2-8), and were diagnosed with consensus. Modified AgNOR staining was performed on tissues including paraffin. Dyeing with AgNOR was accomplished by mixing 2 volumes of 50% silver nitrate with one volume of 2% gelatin and 1% formic acid followed by immediate incubation of the slides in this mixture for 30 minutes. The nuclei were light yellow stained and the outline of the nucleus and cells was clearly visible. AgNOR was visualized as brown-black dots of

variable size within the nuclei. AgNOR was counted in one hundred cells per sample and differences in size and distribution were recorded. AgNOR (mAgNOR) mean and AgNOR (pAgNOR) percentage were calculated. The number of mAgNOR greater than 3.5 indicated high malignant potential. Three dim sections were obtained and AgNOR technique was used according to Ploton et al and further modified by Bukhari et al by minor additional modifications. To briefly describe the method, after waxing and rehydration, the slides were washed in deionized water for 5 minutes. The slides were exposed to silver staining. Dyeing with AgNOR was scored independently by two specialist surgical pathologists. The interobserver agreement was evaluated and a significant agreement was found between the observers.

Classification of dimension change and distribution of AgNOR were performed according to the latest published criteria. AgNOR staining method, tumor type, disease degree, stage or outcome of the two researchers did not have information about the AgNOR, the number, size and distribution performed. Two accounts were made. The first number was the average number of AgNORs in 100 tumor nuclei (mAgNOR). The second number is the percentage of nuclei showing five or more granules of AgNOR / core / 100 cells called the proliferation index (pAgNOR). This number was believed to represent proliferative activity. Tumors with a PAGNOR of 8% or more were considered to have high proliferative activity. The AgNOR proliferation index (pAgNOR) was calculated as the percentage of cells with five or more AgNOR sites. Differences in the size of the AgNOR scores: 0 = More or less smooth, 1+ = Two different sizes, 2+ = More than two different sizes (but not 3+), 3+ = Small enough to be counted in any quality and size. Scattering of AgNOR points: 0 = limited to nucleoli, 1+ = occasional scattering out of nucleoli, 2+ = moderate scattering outside the nucleoli, 3+ = widely distributed throughout the nucleus.

RESULTS:

The mean age of the patients was 39.9 ± 15.1 , ranging from 12 to 80 years. There were 37 (76%) males and 13 (25%) females in this study. There were follicular histopathological variables in 30 men, plexiform varieties in 3, desmoplastic in 2 and acanthomatous ameloblastomas in 2 patients. In addition, there were 10 females with follicle, 1 with plexiform, desmoplastic and acanthomatous (Table 1).

Table 1: Mean age, sex, mAgNOR and pAgNOR counts in different variants of ameloblastoma

Histological variants	Mean age (Year)	Gender (n=50)		Mean Values	
		Male	Female	mAgNOR	pAgNOR
Follicular	39.7±15.8	30	10	1.39±0.82	2.64±1.21
Plexiform	39.8±25.0	3	1	1.62±0.72	2.60±0.69
Desmoplastic	37.3±16.6	2	1	3.05±0.05	5.73±0.32
Acanthomatous	39.3±10.3	2	1	3.15±0.30	8.43±0.80
Total		37	13	P < 0.001	P < 0.001

When AgNOR's mean values were examined in 4 study groups, the mean value of AgNOR was higher for acanthomatous, ie 3.15 ± 0.30 and the follicular variant was lower for 1.39 ± 0.82 . The MAgNOR comparison was performed using ANOVA and the mAgNOR mean was different in 4 groups, p value

was calculated to be <0.001 (Table 1). In the histological variants, the association of mAgNOR 3.0 value was observed when the association of threshold value was observed ($p = 0.003$). The cases with MAgNOR > 3.0 were only in the desmoplastic and acanthomatous groups (Table 2).

Table 2: Histological variants having mAgNOR and pAgNOR more than or less than or equal to normal

Histological variant	mAgNOR		pAgNOR		Total
	≤ 3.0	>3.0	≤ 5.0	> 5.0	
Follicular	40	0	39	1	40
Plexiform	4	0	4	0	4
Desmoplastic	1	2	0	3	3
Acanthomatous	2	1	0	3	3
Total	47	3	43	7	50

mAgNOR P-value = 0.003 and pAgNOR P-value < 0.001

Similarly, the relationship of pAgNOR > 5.0 was significant with histological variants ($P < 0.001$). All desmoplastic and acanthomatous cases had pAgNOR > 5.0 (Table 2). The size relation, histological variables were significant with p value of

0.001. When the desmoplastics were within the +1 and +2 dimensions, the acanthomatous was only +2. There were very few follicular cases in the +1 dimension (Table 3).

Table 3: Comparison of AgNOR size in variants of ameloblastoma

Histological variant	Size			Total
	0	+1	+2	
Follicular	34	6	0	40
Plexiform	4	0	0	4
Desmoplastic	0	2	1	3
Acanthomatous	0	0	3	3
Total	38	8	4	50

P-value = 0.001, 0=More or less uniform, 1+=Two different sizes, 2+=More than two different sizes, 3+=All grades and sizes including too minute to be counted

Similar results were found for the dispersion to be $p < 0.001$ with histological variants (Table 4).

Table 4: Comparison of AgNOR dispersion in different variants of ameloblastoma

Histological variant	Size			Total
	0	+1	+2	
Follicular	38	2	0	40
Plexiform	4	0	0	4
Desmoplastic	1	1	1	3
Acanthomatous	0	1	2	3
Total	43	4	3	50

P-value <0.001, 0=Limited to nucleoli, 1+=Occasional dispersion outside the nucleoli, 2+=Moderate dispersion outside the nucleoli, 3+=Widely dispersed throughout the nucleus

Most of the patients (90%) had tumors in the jaw and maxilla in 10% (Table 5).

Table 5: The most common site for histological different variants of ameloblastoma

Histological variant	Site	
	Mandible	Maxilla
Follicular	36	4
Plexiform	4	0
Desmoplastic	3	0
Acanthomatous	2	1
Total	45 (90%)	5 (10%)

According to our results, if mAgNOR was less than 3, pAgNOR was less than 5%, size and distribution were zero. Such variables were placed in low grade. However, if mAgNOR was more than 3, then

pAgNOR was greater than 5%, size and distribution were more than zero. Such variants were placed in high-grade variants (Table 6).

Table-6: Criteria for Grading of Ameloblastoma

Grade	mAgNOR	pAgNOR	Size	dispersion
Low	<3	<5%	0	0
High	>3	>5%	Equal or > +1	Equal or > +1

Thus, with the help of the AgNOR index, DA and AA were classified as high-grade varieties, while FA

and PA were subdivided into low-grade categories (Table 7).

Table 7: Grading of different variants of Ameloblastoma

Grade	Variants of ameloblastoma
Low grade	Follicular
	Plexiform
High grade	Desmoplastic
	Acanthomatous

The pain was not recorded in 42.86% of the follicular type, 66.7% in desmoplastic, 100% in acanthomatous types and none in plexiform type.

DISCUSSION:

This study was carried out with AgNOR staining technique to determine the proliferation activity of different ameloblastoma variants and the possible correlation of different ameloblastoma variants with clinical behavior with histological malignant potential [6]. 50 cases contained ameloblastoma. In

our study, most of the patients were between the third and fourth decade of life and this is very similar to previous studies [7]. Male dominance was in 50 cases and 33 in men. Most studies on ameloblastoma provide the superiority on men [8]. However, some studies differ from this statement. According to our study, the most common site for the development of ameloblastoma was the jaw that was suitable for the studies previously reported⁹. The number and morphological characteristics of AgNOR are thought to reflect cellular proliferative activity and degree of

malignancy. Follicular was the most common and benign ameloblastoma type (mAgNOR = 1.39, pAgNOR = 2.64, size = 0, range = 0). Because mAgNOR and pAgNOR were insignificant. Similar plexiform model (mAgNOR = 1.62, pAgNOR 2.60, size) = 0, distribution = 0) also showed a negligible variety. However, compared to the acanthomatous varieties (mAgNOR = 3.15, pAgNOR = 8.43, size = + 2, dispersion = +2) and desmoplastics (mAgNOR = 3.05, pAgNOR = 5.73, size = +2, dispersion = +1) and also the other two with the variable, the difference was quite clear. Both types showed significant values in the proliferation index [10-11]. In AgNOR, the percentage per hundred cells and the percentage of points per face area, scattering increased as a malignant potential emerged [12]. Similarly, size and distribution were also significant in these cases. A positive correlation was observed between the DNA index and the average number of nucleolar organization regions [13]. Furthermore, it has been found that the number of average maximum nucleolar promoter regions tends to increase for each increasing rate of dysplasia. In our study, we observed that the average AgNOR and proliferative AgNOR were directly proportional to each other. Some studies have shown that AgNOR numbers correlate well with the number of cells in the S phase with DNA flow cytometry, while another reported a positive relationship between the average AgNOR number and the grade ratio per core [14]. Therefore, the numbers of AgNOR may possibly be associated with cellular activity. The average number of AgNORs gradually increased as the degrees and stages of the tumors increased. The previous study was similar to our study that mAgNOR is directly proportional to the malignant potential of the tumor. Dimension and distribution also have a very important effect on the character of a tumor. AgNOR's small size, large numbers and infrequent distribution are characteristic of malignant tumor cells; whereas the large size, small numbers and grouped distribution of AgNOR are the distinguishing feature of benign tumor cells [15]. The above studies have highlighted the importance of the size and distribution of AgNOR in malignant neoplasms. Previously, some authors have tried to classify AgNOR's size and distribution for benign and malignant decisions. In this study, we follow this method to classify AgNOR size and distribution. AgNOR size and dispersion were significantly higher in acanthomatous and desmoplastic ameloblastoma variants than follicular and plexiform varieties.

CONCLUSION:

The AgNOR staining technique may be useful in the histopathological classification of ameloblastoma.

The quantitative and qualitative evaluation of silver nitrate staining reflects a more malignant potential in acanthomatous and desmoplastic variants than in follicular and plexiform varieties. The AgNOR painting technique is undoubtedly effective, easy to repeat and economical. Use in laboratories should be routinely encouraged. However, even to demonstrate its effectiveness, we need large-scale multicentre studies that use a large sample size. However, in the future, further follow-up clinical study should be performed ideally.

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